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Additional file: Illustrative extracts and respective codes, themes and sub-themes in the social media content analyzed.

Extract	Codes	Themes/sub-themes
MAJOR THEME 1) Sugar-related concerns, beliefs and practices 1.1. Parent-focused content Pregnancy		
France		
[talking about pregnancy cravings] <i>for my son, it was cucumber, tomato with a lot of vinegar and pepper, that's it, especially salty things. Then for my daughter it was the opposite, everything sugary, like sweets, cake, chocolate [...]</i>	Sugar cravings indicating the (female) sex of the baby during pregnancy	Cravings Gendered connotation
France	Comparing efforts of a sugar-free diet with the efforts to quit alcohol	Drug addiction metaphor
<i>Me too, I had gestational diabetes; it is hard in the beginning, especially because the body complains due to the addiction, until the addiction goes away. It is like with alcoholics, when they withdraw it's hard for them, the body complains. Well, with sugar it is the same.</i>		Gestational diabetes
France	Replacing cigarettes with sugar to quit smoking	Smoke cessation
<i>I quit smoking for my pregnancy but I replaced the cigarette with sugar!</i>		
France	Dangers of artificial sweeteners (in light products) during pregnancy	Artificial sweeteners and light products
[Post]: <i>Pregnant women tend to drink more light soft drinks in an attempt to limit their sugar intake. According to a study from Inserm, light soft drinks are not as harmless as it is believed, since they could increase risk of type 2 diabetes. Another concern: lovers of these drinks, who perceive them as "healthier", might consume them in big quantities. Are you going to change your habits?</i>	Confusion, misconceptions	Dietary cacophony
Some comments to this included: <i>I drink coke but in a normal way! [...] ! I prefer to drink a good glass of normal coke from time to time than to consume the light version every day</i> <i>I drink light and I will continue</i>	Diverse practices Concerns about sugar alternatives	
France	Pregnancy as a situation to allow food indulgences	Gastronomic pleasure of sugar
[reacting to a post where a pregnant woman complained to feel constantly hungry during pregnancy]		
<i>Eat, do yourself some good! Pregnancy is the only time when women can let go a little, so take advantage of it!!! You will be careful afterwards!!!</i>		Pursuit of enjoyment

<p><i>I'm hungry all the time too but I'm not pregnant myself 😊 take advantage of having an excuse (valid or not) to make yourself happy ...</i></p> <p><i>Well sister, eat, allow yourself not to care, it's the only time when you can eat without being told something and without guilt, so take advantage</i></p> <p><i>Eat dear sister!!!! A good cake 😊</i></p> <p><i>Take advantage of having an excuse to please yourself ...</i></p> <p><i>It's exactly the period where we can let go without too much "remorse": p</i></p>	<p>Gastronomic pleasures enjoyed without social judgment and guilt during pregnancy</p> <p>Cravings constructed as beyond control</p>	<p>Food indulgences</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>In pregnancy, I broke loose and ate just about everything I wanted</i></p> <p><i>I can't control my sugar intake at all. It's unhealthy for me and the baby. Plus I have put on 20kg!!!!</i></p> <p><i>If I wasn't pregnant, then I would join [the sugar free period]! But, a sugar stop under these conditions is inhumane</i></p>	<p>Impossible to make the right choice during pregnancy</p> <p>Judgment, frustration, distress</p>	<p>Maternal judgment</p> <p>Negative emotions</p>
<p>France</p> <p><i>When we are pregnant, we are not allowed anything!!! Everything we do is bad!!</i></p> <p><i>What is worse is that, once you give birth, it's the same! Everything you do is criticized!</i></p>	<p>Discouraging the consumption of fruit</p> <p>Employing scientific terms to explain avoidance of fruit</p>	<p>Fruit restrictions</p> <p>Cravings</p> <p>Scientific terms</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>This whole sugar debate is actually something I've been insanely insecure about, and I feel that no matter what you do, someone will judge you for the choices you make ...</i></p>	<p>Extract</p>	<p>Codes</p>
<p>MAJOR THEME 1) Sugar-related concerns, beliefs and practices</p> <p>1.1. Parent-focused content</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Weight loss and sugar-free diet</p>		
<p>France</p>		

<p><i>It's final, I will become sugar free! We all know now that sugar is a kind of modern poison, it is everywhere and it is bad for your health.</i></p> <p><i>I want to detox from sugar in order to purify my body and be healthier.</i></p> <p><i>I like the idea of detoxifying my body and the bodies of my children ...</i></p> <p><i>I also try to limit [sugar] as much as possible for my children. I myself, I am a sugar addict, and that is not manner of speech! I am in permanent withdrawal, I relapse constantly, it is very hard</i></p> <p><i>I have a friend who did it (1-month challenge without sugar) in a strict way (excluding even fruit) to treat a candidiasis; she said that the 1st week was much more difficult than quitting cigarettes! This diet put her in a dog mood and more (proof that it is a real drug in my opinion) ...</i></p>	<p>Sugar as a poison, a drug, a toxic substance to be detoxified from the body Comparing efforts of a sugar-free diet with the efforts to quit cigarettes</p> <p>Sugar as dangerous, toxic</p>	<p>Health effect: addiction</p> <p>Drug addiction metaphor</p> <p>Detox from sugar</p> <p>Restriction on fruit</p> <p>Meanings attributed to sugar</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>So NOW I am on sugar weaning! Have already thrown out cake remnants (instead of stuffing myself with them for breakfast)</i></p> <p><i>You know, we sugar addicts get incredibly creative when it comes to getting the "white gold"!</i></p> <p><i>I kept it clean for a week where I was seriously angry and had no sense of humor.</i></p>	<p>Flexibility in the sugar-free period</p> <p>Fruit and dark chocolate not counting as sugar sources</p> <p>Sugar in homemade meals as legitimate</p>	<p>Distancing from extreme practices</p> <p>Fruit</p> <p>Homemade foods/home cooking</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p>[in response to a sugar-free period testimonial]</p> <p><i>By the way, the rules for my sugar stop are simple: Fruit sugar does not count as sugar, and chocolate with a cocoa percentage above 70 does not count as chocolate! You can say what you like, but it works for me.</i></p> <p><i>Your method considering that fruit sugar is not sugar and that chocolate 70% cacao is also included, sounds like something you can actually endure.</i></p> <p><i>Sugar in food doesn't count either, I still eat sugar on my oatmeal, and I won't start baking cakes without sugar</i></p> <p><i>Therefore, my end date for this sugar stop is December 1st! When I follow these [flexible] rules, it doesn't feel like a prison or a punishment, and I'm more likely to implement it.</i></p>	<p>Extract</p>	<p>Codes</p> <p>Furtive, clandestine, transgressive aspects of sugar</p> <p>Feelings of guilt</p>
<p>France</p> <p><i>Sugar is Satan!</i></p> <p><i>Satanic drug</i></p> <p><i>Chocolate is my sin, my guilty pleasure</i></p> <p>[chocolate is] <i>Temptation in its pure form</i></p> <p><i>☹☹☹ no, you're not alone, I too am weak, I just succumbed to a Milka chocolate bar</i></p>	<p>Themes/sub-themes</p>	<p>Religious words and expressions</p> <p>Religious metaphor</p> <p>Negative emotions</p>

<p><i>I also declare myself guilty: I'm checking out Facebook while taking a coffee break, necessarily accompanied by sweetness (Toblerone) 😊😊😊</i></p> <p><i>Oops, I sinned 😊😊😊 [I am] addicted too, it's a torment</i></p>		
Denmark		
<p><i>I ate a wine gum on Tuesday. Just one and was burdened with a bad conscience [...] so I hurried to write a text and confess my sin, haha.</i></p> <p><i>I live a sinful sugar life myself. Every single day I eat either candy or cake. Every. Single. Day.</i></p> <p><i>Because in these finger-pointing and sugar-phobic times we live in, there are almost similarities between sugar and cocaine. "The White Devil". "Sugar-Satan".</i></p>		
France		
<p><i>I lost weight very quickly after my third baby, just by reducing the sugar.</i></p> <p><i>In the end [of sugar-free period], I lost 1.5 kilos. Which I think is a lot considering that I continued to eat like crazy.</i></p> <p><i>My husband and I, we lost 5 kg each just by cutting juice, liqueurs and iced tea, in addition to the jujubes [kind of confectionary sweets].</i></p> <p><i>I really noticed that by limiting sugar a lot, I was much more energetic and in good shape (not mentioning getting thinner). Try it!</i></p> <p><i>Very good experience for me, it's been a year since I've consumed refined sugar or cow's milk, my children too. So much happier I feel! ...</i></p> <p><i>I add more: when we remove sugar and salt, we end up finding the real taste of food.</i></p>	<p>Positive experiences with sugar-detox period: weight loss, increased energy levels, palate education, happiness</p>	<p>Sugar-free diet satisfaction</p>
Extract		
France		
<p><i>A few years ago, I had a "sugar free" week, I had lost 1.5 kilos, I felt better, but I felt such a need that made me fall back into it fairly quickly.</i></p> <p><i>I know for a long time that, by depriving myself of sugar, I will have an urgent need to indulge myself. So I know I have to be careful not to get frustrated. It would be catastrophic; I would regain all the kilos lost in less time than it takes to lose them.</i></p>	<p>Regaining weight after sugar-free diet</p> <p>Inner conflict between cravings and fear for health and weight gain</p>	<p>Inner conflict with health/indulgence dilemma</p>
France		
<p><i>I feel the same.... strongly at the end of the school holidays I cannot take it anymore with all this sugar in the house</i></p>	<p>Motherhood imposing barriers to decrease sugar consumption due to availability of sweets in</p>	<p>Barriers for sugar reduction</p>

<p><i>First day of the holidays... I definitely already deserve a good dose of sugar! Cheers to all those who are waiting for only one thing: back to school... [Posted with a picture saying "Keep calm and eat M & M's"]</i></p> <p><i>It's true that with children it's hard not to buy cookies.</i></p>	<p>the house, stress and social activities related to early maternity</p>	<p>Social aspects</p> <p>Negative emotions</p>
<p>Denmark</p>		
<p><i>There are a lot of temptations in sweet maternity life ☺</i></p> <p><i>I could do it [sugar free period] by the way before I had kids, but since then it has simply gone nuts!</i></p> <p><i>I gained two kilos after the last maternity leave, because there was so much cake and chocolate involved in mothers' social life! It requires determination to say no thanks.</i></p>		
<p>Extract</p>	<p>Codes</p>	<p>Themes/sub-themes</p>
<p>France</p>		
<p><i>I have a "low GI [Glycemic Index]" book, which is really great for ideas to replace sugar with other stuff.</i></p> <p><i>Juices are source of huge amounts of sugar, without fibers ... Even natural and sugar-free juices are not recommended and can lead to caries ... Nothing is better than real fruit!</i></p> <p><i>Sugar from either candy or juice has the same impact on our body.</i></p> <p><i>So, this book has recipes for sweet dishes without any sugar. I find the approach a bit extreme, because it is not just refined sugars that are eliminated but ALL sugars (honey, agave syrup, fructose, everything ...), replaced by natural sweeteners (xylitol and stevia).</i></p> <p><i>There is coconut sugar which is awesome, and it's whole, complete sugar, it has a lower [glycemic?] index than refined sugar</i></p> <p><i>As the [link to a webpage] explains, there is a big difference between complex carbohydrates (grains, legumes) and the sugar of fruits (not juices) versus added refined sugar. Our brain runs on carbohydrates, we just need to know how to give it the right ones ;)</i></p> <p><i>People make me laugh, there is sugar even in milk, damn</i></p>	<p>Employment of scientific and medical terms to discuss the (un) healthiness of sugar, sugar replacers and sources (fruit juices)</p> <p>Referring to sources of knowledge about sugar</p> <p>Referring to sugar origin and source, processing and metabolic effects</p> <p>Expressing contradiction, confusion and frustration</p>	<p>Scientific and medical terms</p> <p>Knowledge sources</p> <p>Fruit juices</p> <p>Sugar replacers</p> <p>Confusion about the definition of sugar</p> <p>Dietary cacophony</p> <p>Negative emotions</p>
<p>Denmark</p>		
<p>[blog post] <i>HOW MUCH SUGAR DO YOU EAT – AND YOUR CHILDREN?</i></p> <p><i>Do you check how much you sugar – and your children eat? WHO recommends that a maximum of 10% of the total energy comes from sugar – and points out that a 5% limit would probably be even better, but it is not quite documented enough yet.</i></p> <p><i>[...] Secondly, fruit sugar is not just fruit sugar. Different fruits have different effects on the blood sugar. For example, apple has a positive effect on blood sugar and helps keep it stable, while watermelon runs straight into the blood like white sugar.</i></p>		

<p><i>But most carbohydrates are converted into glucose in the body – this is how the body works :-) When we talk about sugar, we mean sugar from the beginning (before it gets in your mouth). And agree, sugar is not just sugar. There are many different kinds.</i></p> <p><i>[in reaction to a figure showing the amount of sugar in products] So the quantities in the table are all sugar (including fruit sugar and milk sugar)? Do not think you are completely clear in the table. I agree that young children should not have sugar, but they cannot completely avoid it in the food. Would be nice if you wrote a little about how much the quantities correspond to, for example, different types of fruit and how bad smoothies are.</i></p>		
<p>France</p> <p><i>I'm not sure that giving a false sweet taste to food [by using artificial sweeteners] helps the brain to get rid of cravings for something sweet ... I'm not a fan of the concept of sweeteners. For me, what worked was just to "update my software". I convinced my brain (more important than my stomach, in the case of sugar!) that it didn't need that sweet taste after every meal, for example. My brain complained for the first few days, but then it got on the right track ☺.</i></p> <p><i>I think the issue here [in the online discussion] is mostly about Xylitol. I have no knowledge that it is a bad product, on the contrary, even if indeed, it is necessary to extract it in a more or less natural way to obtain a product similar to sugar for sweet purposes :)</i></p> <p><i>According to my dietician, sweeteners are not so great because they signal to the brain the same message (and therefore calories) as sugar, but the brain [in spite of the message] will find itself without sugar, it will order production of insulin when there is no need ...</i></p> <p><i>my dietician asked me to throw it all away, sweeteners, light products, etc. etc. ... :-) But ok, stevia, it's natural, I have no idea if it is found in "light" products</i></p>	<p>Discussion of healthiness and naturalness of artificial sweeteners and sugar replacers</p> <p>Concerns about healthiness of alternatives</p>	<p>Artificial sweeteners</p> <p>Sugar replacers</p> <p>Scientific terms</p>
<p>France</p> <p><i>Isn't Canderel aspartame? It's super chemical, right? I'm going to try coconut sugar ...</i></p> <p><i>I thought it was better to use agave syrup, honey, etc. than sweeteners! : o</i></p> <p><i>Is it good, agave syrup? It does not inspire much trust in me ... ☺</i></p>	<p>Expressing confusion and disagreement on healthiness of sugar-related products</p> <p>Concerns about healthiness of alternatives</p>	<p>Artificial sweeteners</p> <p>Sugar replacers</p> <p>Dietary cacophony</p>
<p>France</p> <p><i>you have coconut sugar which is great and whole, complete sugar, it has a lower [glycemic?] index than refined sugar</i></p> <p><i>We switched to unrefined (but really raw!) sugar, it helps!</i></p> <p><i>So here we use maple syrup or whole cane sugar.</i></p>	<p>Coconut sugar and cane sugar considered healthy due to "wholeness" and "completeness"</p>	<p>Sugar replacers</p>
<p>France</p>		

<p>[comments to a post of a recipe using artificial sweeteners instead of sugar] <i>Sweetener is sugar It's not sugar-free your recipe ;)</i></p> <p><i>By "sugar" I thought she meant "refined sugar" when she said "any existing form of sugar" damn! 8 sachets of sweetener !!! It must be sweet, hey! I'll try, but with real sugar</i></p>	<p>Confusion and disagreement about the definition of sugar</p> <p>Encouraging consumption of fruit (Denmark)</p>	<p>Confusion on the definition of sugar</p> <p>Dietary cacophony</p> <p>Fruit</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>White sugar is noticeable. As mentioned, fruit also contains sugar, but fruit sugar. First, fruit sugar has a different chemical structure than white sugar, and the body can benefit from it in a completely different way.</i></p>		
<p>France</p> <p><i>I reduced my sugar consumption drastically. When I say drastically, it's the right word ... neither refined sugar, nor natural sugar (no fruit, nor fruit juice either). We must transfer the pleasure of sweet to other pleasures: that of eating good products, vegetables from local markets, etc. ...</i></p>	<p>Discouraging the consumption of fruit</p> <p>Pleasure from vegetables</p>	<p>Restriction on fruit</p>
Extract	Codes	Themes/sub-themes
<p>MAJOR THEME 1) Sugar-related concerns, beliefs and practices</p> <p>1.1. Parent-focused content</p> <p>Negative emotions</p>		
<p>France</p> <p><i>Just like you, I eat healthy but I cannot do without chocolate, a big piece a day or even two (on days when I'm down)</i></p> <p><i>That's how it is, as soon as I get tired or upset: SUGAR.</i></p> <p><i>I feel very well that I eat it [sugar] to relieve stress.</i></p> <p><i>[sugar consumption] it's all because of worrying. Stop eating to calm your emotions, but do what instead? Fatigue also makes you want sugar</i></p>	<p>Sugar consumption due to feelings of depression, fatigue, stress, worries.</p>	<p>Negative emotions</p> <p>Hedonic aspect</p> <p>Reward</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>[...] on maternity leave with a baby that has kept me awake almost continuously for 5 months, I do not survive without anything sweet. Dessert instead of lunch is the best time of the day!</i></p> <p><i>I eat chocolate every single day, preferably two (three) pieces. And my head always has a good 'excuse' (tired, work, it's MONDAY, etc.)</i></p>		
<p>France</p> <p><i>We are very good eaters (especially me, you may have noticed!) And it is totally unthinkable to do without sweetness and a sweet taste which gives so much satisfaction to the palate as to the spirits ...</i></p> <p><i>Sugar is life, isn't it??</i></p>	<p>Sugar as comfort, love, taste, happiness, pleasure</p> <p>Positive meanings attributed to sugar</p>	<p>Hedonic aspects</p> <p>Symbolic value of sugar</p>

<p><i>I will never ban myself 100%, it [sugar] is one of my great pleasures in life</i></p> <p><i>I am fully aware of the harmful nature of sugar, but I loooove it ^^ so for me it's enough to limit it a little, but sincerely it is part of the pleasures of life, right? :)</i></p> <p><i>It's reassuring, comforting to eat ☺☺✍</i></p> <p><i>[sugar] It's comfort, like a cuddle ... and a habit.</i></p> <p><i>Just a little every day, it seems to make the brain happy ☺</i></p>		Pursuit of enjoyment
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>And I get up every morning and am tempted to put some sugar = love in my son's lunch box.</i></p> <p><i>candy and cake are also related to e.g. joy or comfort</i></p> <p><i>[dark chocolate] is healthy. Especially for the soul.</i></p>		
Extract	Codes	Themes/sub-themes
<p>France</p> <p><i>As soon as I feel emotional (which happens quite often when one is hyper-emotional ...) ouch, I eat.</i></p>	Fondness of sugar associated with personality traits	Concept of self
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>You can be a good mother even if the children have a pancake, chocolate or other life's delicious temptations – because I LOVE being with my kids around the table in the afternoon for a "forbidden" pancake and a chat about life. And if [my son] shouts "more" then he gets one more pancake. "</i></p> <p><i>I think we have gotten ourselves completely messed up as a society, the fact that we need to have fun, that we should treat ourselves, that there should be room for a little sweet, or that we should not at least deny us anything.</i></p> <p><i>I would very much like to limit the intake of sugar more than it is, but I think it is incredibly difficult when our society is like that, in order to enjoy yourself, you have to have something with sugar in it. When you think about it, it is basically strange.</i></p>	Defending/ opposing cultural and social association of sugary foods with coziness and joy	<p><i>Hygge</i></p> <p>Sugar in the Danish coziness</p> <p>Social aspects</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>I just had both a big Twix and a big Mars bar the other day, have no idea why or what they tasted like and the tummy ache afterwards really made me regret it</i></p> <p><i>I've been thinking the same thoughts about the fact that sugar just suddenly is something you eat to eat it, but not because you REALLY feel like it – and so it is silly and stupid.</i></p>	<p>Sugar consumption as a habit, not necessarily good, leading to regret</p> <p>Not consciously enjoying, savoring sweets</p>	<p>Sugar as an “stupid” habit</p> <p>Regret</p>

Extract	Codes	Themes/sub-themes
MAJOR THEME 1) Sugar-related concerns, beliefs and practices 1.1. Parent-focused content		
Potential health risks (in Figure 1)		
France <i>I study sugar in my laboratory and it blows my mind every day to be aware of such a crisis: we bathe in sugar, it's a crime (look at school canteens ☹️) our children are completely addicted</i> <i>Yes, again about sugar, and yes we demonize sugar. Because let's be honest, sugar does not do anything good! Millions of adults (including me) suffer from sugar addiction because of a childhood with too much sugar</i> <i>It is not an urban legend that chocolate overexcites.... my 6-year-old son, his pupils dilate and he jumps against the walls like a ball !! Damn!!!</i> <i>My daughter, she runs everywhere, sings, turns in circles, forgets that sleeping is an option, loses all her good habits ... all this after 2 cookies and a mini piece of chocolate cake ...</i> [sugar is] <i>the secret of hyperactivity, but hush!</i> [sugar] <i>is a poison, we know today that Alzheimer's disease has its origin in the consumption of sugar (among other factors)</i> <i>Just for information, cancer cells feed on sugars</i> <i>By the way, sugar is one of the first risk factors of type 2 diabetes</i> <i>Sugar (glucose-modified corn syrup) is what contributes to obesity and diabetes</i> [I have been] <i>addicted to sugar since childhood to the delight of my dentist</i>	Addiction, hyperactivity, Alzheimer, cancer, diabetes, obesity, caries.	Potential health risks: diseases, behavioral changes
Denmark <i>The movie came with a point that has really stuck with me. At one point, an experiment was made with 43 cocaine-dependent mice that had been given free access to both cocaine and sugar water. In just 15 days, 40 out of the 43 mice preferred the sugar water. Sugar is thus more addictive than cocaine! MORE!</i> <i>I just went to the dentist today and there were TWO cavities for the first time in many years ... I 'm trembling already and fear Thursday [referring to Thursday/Friday candy]... And yes, I eat way too much sugar, so I'll say</i>		

<p><i>"No thanks" to sugar for the next three weeks</i></p> <p><i>Who really wants a future with obesity and diabetes?</i></p>		
<p>France</p> <p><i>[my daughter has] never tasted industrial sweet products. And she's doing well. Children have an entire life ahead to taste sweet things, so give them the right food instincts from the start</i></p> <p><i>I add more: when we remove sugar and salt, we end up finding the real taste of food.</i></p> <p><i>Well, when they [the food industry] stop adding sugar everywhere, children will automatically consume less sugar</i></p> <p><i>Same here, zero candy, only water or pomegranate juice / fresh orange juice, cookies and cakes low in sugar, mashed fruit instead of jam, dark chocolate instead of milk chocolate. Our 3-year-old son loves it and he is not missing out on anything because his palate has been educated, it has not been overwhelmed with sugar</i></p> <p><i>When we don't do like the majority, we are criticized. [...] Our 3-year-old son adores healthy foods, and it is not a torture because his palate has been educated not to be submerged in sugar ...</i></p>	<p>Restriction of sugar for palate education, to prevent the palatability of healthy foods</p>	<p>Potential health risks: addiction; decreased palatability</p> <p>Avoiding highly processed foods</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>But he [son] does not get juice, soft drinks, sweets, sun-lollies [sherbet] etc. like many others, because we want him to have a balanced relationship with sugar and not get a sweet tooth early.</i></p> <p><i>Many children have difficulty getting real foods. They are not used to eating things that are not sweet.</i></p>		
<p>France</p> <p><i>In my case, my oldest when she eats sugar, she is not overexcited but very arrogant, she listens to nothing, talks back, acts stubborn, does everything that she is not supposed to. After 2-3 days without sugar, everything is ok.</i></p> <p><i>When my children eat sugar, they don't feel sick, but VERY pissed off !!! Honestly I can't wait for the routine to resume tomorrow :) [after festivities]</i></p>	<p>Disobedience, arrogance, anger, less focused, irritation, depression</p>	<p>Potential health risks: behavioral changes</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>Large amounts of sugar make the child hyper [active] [...] and it can make it more difficult for the child to focus and learn [...] So too much sugar can affect the whole child both body and mind.</i></p> <p><i>I ate 500 ml chocolate ice cream yesterday in about 10 min. After which I felt incredibly bad (headache, irritable, depressed ... my body went completely cold)</i></p>		

Extract	Codes	Themes/sub-themes
MAJOR THEME 1) Sugar-related concerns, beliefs and practices 1.2 Child-focused content <p style="text-align: center;">Festivities</p>		
France <p>[mentioning another mother from the group] <i>precisely as you say: control the quantities! This is exactly what [another mother from the same group] does. Instead of exceeding, she controls the intake of chocolate with other things. She does not say to not to give sweets, chocolates or anything like that. She says precisely to moderate, even at parties. It doesn't mean that there will be no candies, just not 5kg of chocolate per child.</i></p> Denmark <p><i>The social factor is a huge player, which is why we all have a responsibility. Not just to our own children, but for example, what we teach children about socializing and what it means to "have fun".</i></p> <p><i>Now get rid of eco-ladies with their fruit chips. It is probably their children who will go crazy for sweets, coke and chips at parties because they have never had anything. Everything in moderation.</i></p> <p><i>We can agree that sweets, cakes, etc. are completely useless food. But we all eat it after all. Why?? Because it tastes good – and not least because it is nice to socialize! This is what I want to pass on to my child – in appropriate doses, of course! ”</i></p>	Defending moderated sugar consumption during festivities Defending social aspects of sugar consumption	Behavioral strategy: moderation Socialized sugar consumption Social aspects
France [Post] <i>At Easter, children wolf down sugar. What if we offered them something else? Here are some ideas to replace chocolate.</i>	Post offering ideas for gifts to replace chocolates during Easter Sharing alternatives to decrease sugar offering	Restriction of sugar during festivities
France <i>My kids really don't eat much sugar regularly, and I was disturbed to see my youngest completely high. Next year I warn those around me: no junk! My girls will eat the very minimum! It's awful to consciously drug our children! Sugar is the worst drug there is!</i> <i>Yes I am anti-candy, there is Halloween, Christmas, Easter holidays. Hold the candy.</i>	Sugar restriction justified on the grounds of its addictive and “nefarious” properties Sugar as a drug	Behavioral strategy: restriction Meanings attributed to sugar
France		

<p><i>Ok Easter is just once a year, but if we combine the thousands of children's and family's celebrations over the year where there are cakes and sweets. Halloween, Christmas, etc. Each of them is just once a year. It's funny this thought of "ah let it go, it's just once a year!" I hear it 26 times a year.</i></p> <p><i>Oh, there is nothing to worry about ... really? My child eats it [candy] in Halloween, Easter, Valentine's Day, Christmas, New Year's Day, at his birthday party, during summer vacation, at grannie's, at granddaddy's, at the restaurant ... It's pitiful !</i></p>	<p>Too many holidays to justify free consumption</p> <p>Expressing distress about too many celebrations with sugar involved</p>	<p>Behavioral strategy: restriction</p> <p>Social aspects, social norms</p>
<p>Denmark</p>		
<p><i>After all, it was Friday and we needed to have some fun, or it was birthday, fasting, Easter, cold, hot, you name it.</i></p>		
<p>France</p>		
<p><i>Just stop encouraging these commercial parties, which are meaningless to most people!!</i></p> <p><i>This year I decided to change, and I bought games that will last, uggh, long; instead of chocolate. But the other parents are not "bad" because they give chocolate ... anyway all parties, deep down, are capitalist,...</i></p> <p><i>Can you please stop associating children's pleasure in life with refined sugar? Listen to Sugar Coated [a documentary], sugar is a toxin.</i></p>	<p>Festivities as meaningless commercial, capitalist parties created to encourage overconsumption</p> <p>Defending candy restrictions</p> <p>Sugar as a toxin</p>	<p>Behavioral strategy: restriction</p> <p>Meanings attributed to sugar</p>
<p>France</p>		
<p><i>Most of the chocolates sold are of very poor quality and contribute to accentuate poverty in the world</i></p> <p><i>This year my children will receive artisanal candies made by the autism company [name of the association for children with autism].</i></p>	<p>Chocolate consumption contributes to increase poverty and inequality</p> <p>Alternative: artisanal chocolates</p>	<p>(un)Ethical aspects of chocolate production</p> <p>Ethical alternative to legitimize consumption</p>
<p>France</p>		
<p><i>Kids enjoy egg hunting and plenty of other things even more than chocolate! In addition, they will have something nice to remember!</i></p> <p><i>We have established another ritual rather than chocolate, we give them a little book or a small CD of music to compensate. The ritual is the same, we hide the gifts somewhere and the kids have to find them</i></p> <p><i>No, our youngest cannot eat chocolate, so we offer books, games, books with stickers, everybody wins 😊</i></p> <p><i>This year I proposed to the children to do a family activity and they are happy because they will get candy from others anyway 😊</i></p> <p><i>Since Easter happens at the same time of the beginning of spring, I like to make baskets with things to play outside, bubbles, sidewalk chalks, jump rope ...</i></p>	<p>Alternatives to sugar during festivities: offering of toys, family time and outdoor activities, homemade dishes</p>	<p>Behavioral strategy: restriction</p> <p>Alternatives to sweets</p> <p>Home-made foods</p>

<p><i>My daughter is 3 years old. I said to myself that going out to the movies could be a nice alternative instead of having only Easter chocolate she was allowed a coconut hunt anyway but that's enough for her, she is only 3 year old</i></p> <p><i>I prepare my potatoes myself. Sweet seasoned turnip and homemade fries 😊😊😊😊</i></p> <p><i>I find manufactured food stuff too sweet nowadays (and bah, in taste) but a good artisanal or homemade pastry</i></p>		
Extract	Codes	Themes/sub-themes
Denmark	Homemade desserts as more legitimated and acceptable than confectionary	“Proper” sources of sugar
<p><i>I feel that my children can have sugar, but it must be from a proper "source". Pancakes, which have been mentioned several times, a good homemade cake, ice cream (yummy) or a slab of chocolate on Friday night. We do not buy gummy bears, etc. as I would like them to have some proper "food", with good ingredients</i></p>		Home-made foods
France	Defending liberated consumption of sweets	Behavioral strategy: liberation
<p><i>Poor little ones, enjoy chocolate during Easter, it's perfect</i></p>		
<p><i>Allow the kids to enjoy a little</i></p>	Sweets restriction as an almost cruel deprivation to children	Legitimate consumption at festivities
<p><i>It is only once a year! Its good ! Let's allow our children to live their lives ... We all ate it ...</i></p>		
<p><i>I think the same! We all did it too when we were young and I only have fond memories about Easter, that was family time with lots of chocolates!</i></p>	Own food upbringing as reasons not to restrict	Own food upbringing
<p><i>Hey, damn, why change such beautiful traditions ... after Halloween without candy here comes Easter without chocolate</i></p>	Sugar consumption as legitimate during festivities	Social aspects
Denmark		
<p><i>Great to relax around sugar. Too many parents are just completely frightened, and it is a pity for the little ones who miss something that is a comfort for other children :-)</i></p>		
<p><i>Honestly, I almost think it is a shame when you see such a child looking heartily at an ice-cream or a lollipop because the parents don't want them to eat anything with sugar... ..come on...</i></p>		
<p><i>I grew up in the 1950 and have eaten everything over the years, and I'm still alive. It seems to be too much with all that healthy stuff...no wonder that children have become so picky. My children ate everything and they are living at their best.</i></p>		
<p><i>God father, poor children ...</i></p>		
France	Liberation due to fear of compulsive eating behavior	Behavioral strategy: liberation
<p><i>[mentioning another mother from the group], you're right, it is what people don't understand... The more we deprive and limit our children, the more they compensate later! I saw an interview with parents who restricted their young children, then they showed the children years later</i></p>		

<p><i>Totally agree. I believe that by banishing candy altogether, the result is that children get an abnormal relationship with sugar, as they grow older.</i></p> <p><i>Think we should all relax a bit[...]. In fact, I am convinced that we do the children a damn of a disservice if we teach them that there is something others have / must have, which our children cannot.</i></p>	<p>Opposing deprivation and extreme strategies</p>	<p>Fear of compulsive eating behavior due to restriction</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>I believe that by banishing candy altogether, the result is that your children get an abnormal relationship with sugar as they grow older.</i></p> <p><i>It is only when one is so extreme that children get a screwed-up relationship with food. I think it is sad and pitiful to live by such strict rules.</i></p> <p><i>In my view, children end up having a totally screwed-up relationship with food and it is usually the children who end up not being able to control themselves when they are finally allowed to eat.</i></p> <p><i>I even grew up with a loose relationship with sweets, crisps and all the unhealthy stuff. My parents never told us that we only could have it on weekends, and to a limited extent... Therefore, me and my brother today have a relaxed relationship with unhealthy foods [...] we eat a bit here and there, without going completely crazy.</i></p>		
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>It's just about giving children a healthy approach to what is healthy and unhealthy – at least we do this at our house.</i></p> <p><i>I make sure my son eats all food groups in a day, but no sugar hysteria, and it has resulted in a relaxed relationship with sugar at our house. He has been forbidden nothing, the result is that we can have a bowl [of candies] for two weeks and the kid does not touch it...that's what comes from not being hysterical about sugar.</i></p> <p><i>My son is the one in our family of five who has the most sensible relationship with sugar, sweets and cake. We others have a more uncontrolled intake. Besides Friday Candy, there is not a day when we do not eat sugar in some form in greater quantities than recommended, and we eat a lot more than he does. He has a drawer that is almost always well stocked with Friday candies. He goes and takes a little from the drawer every now and then. Simply because we have eaten all ours, while he eats a little and saves the rest. And then it tends to accumulate a bit. But that's ok ... precisely because he doesn't eats everything at once like we do.</i></p>	<p>Defending children's autonomy to learn how to control sugar intake</p> <p>Opposing deprivation and extreme strategies</p>	<p>Children's autonomy and self-regulation</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>Saturday candy with family; all the soda ice lollies we could eat when we ran barefoot around the garden under the heat of the sun... 😊😊😊</i></p> <p><i>You can get so totally hit by a happiness drunk (or it was all that sugar... or hormones 😊😊) when you sit there in the garden and enjoy your very own family in your own garden and the sound of laughter of the little miracles [the children] (all mothers think their children are miracles) [...] having tri-colored ice cream that you eat from a cup with a spoon and I can tell you that the little ones were in heaven.</i></p>	<p>Culture, tradition and ritual attached to Friday candy and coziness</p>	<p>Friday candy and beyond</p> <p><i>Hygge</i></p> <p>Sugar in the Danish coziness</p>

<p><i>If you have sweets every day, then it will not be something special and extra cozy</i></p> <p><i>We have Friday candy at home, and sometimes Saturday candy. And if we have company on a Sunday, it happens that there is a little bit. Oooh if it is mega hot on weekdays in the summer, we have sun lollies [soda ice lollies] in the freezer ready.</i></p> <p><i>[...] I get so angry when someone wants decide what others must and must not do, where it would otherwise be cozy and enjoyable 😊</i></p> <p><i>At our house, we have a strict policy that sugar only belongs to the weekend. Unfortunately, Thursday is a little Friday and Monday is almost Sunday, and if you are going out for a birthday or coffee, special rules also apply</i></p> <p><i>I used to be the type that would eat the kids' Friday candies (up to several times in a week ...).</i></p> <p><i>Trying to keep it on Friday only, but it does not always work out.</i></p> <p><i>Amen, amen and amen! My sugar policy is pretty loose. Trying to keep it for the weekends, but if we want a cake on Monday afternoon – then we will have a cake. Also the children. And only because I do not agree with a more strict sugar policy</i></p> <p><i>On the other hand, we generally run with "no sweets in everyday life, only Friday" (i.e. for the children ...). BUT...</i></p> <p><i>Only sweets on Friday – no: on the weekend – usually runs no longer than until Tuesday.</i></p>	<p>Defending cultural and social association of sugary foods with coziness and joy</p>	<p>Social aspects</p>
Extract	Codes	Themes/sub-themes
MAJOR THEME 1) Sugar-related concerns, beliefs and practices 1.2 Child-focused content Child feeding concerns		
<p>France</p> <p>[small discussion about the juice and smoothies brand called Innocent]:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The Innocent brand is an absolute horror</i> • <i>This brand produces carbonated drinks?</i> • <i>No, it is a brand of 100% natural fruit juice, quite expensive, but its juices contain 28g of sugar, much more than soft drinks</i> <p><i>They [the children] eat what I buy, I have banned from our lives all products that contain glucose-fructose, modified corn syrup, GMO's and other agents.</i></p> <p>[talking about processed juice] <i>I used to drink it. Until the day when I tasted it at room temperature. When not chilled, it is really disgusting, bah, a real taste of plastic! We must certainly stop giving this carcinogenic shit to our children! There are a thousand other healthier ways to please our children.</i></p>	<p>Parents exchanging information about the composition and (un) healthiness of highly processed foods</p> <p>Food industry as a dangerous force</p>	<p>Highly processed foods</p> <p>Anger towards food manufacturers</p> <p>Marketing responsibility</p>

<p><i>No matter the brand! There's no worse junk than flavored and sweetened yogurts! 1 yogurt = 6 spoons of sugars! (my dietician told me)</i></p> <p><i>Apart from yogurts, there are candies, pseudo cereals in the morning that are more than 50% sugar, etc.</i></p> <p><i>A recent TV show communicated that food manufacturers add sugar to baby food, to create a real addiction in our little ones. There should be better and more strict regulations or at least less deceiving information from the industry</i></p>		
<p>France</p> <p><i>Did you know that for children aged 2 to 8 years old, the average consumption of sugar per day is 101 grams? The book Sugar – Truths and Consequences, by [author], portrays an objective and at the same time, a frightening picture of this food ingredient.</i> [No comments 8 shares]</p> <p><i>We should eat 40 grams of sugar a day and not exceed this limit. That is what, according to the book I read (Detox [author's name] a quite old book I found it in the library), is the maximum amount the body can metabolize without problems.</i></p> <p><i>The second step is to decrease the sugar intake (even healthy sugar) in order to reach the 25g recommended by the WHO, but this step worries me a little concerning children's diet.</i></p>	<p>Discussion of sugar recommendation for children</p> <p>Different sources of recommendations, including health experts and authorities</p> <p>Referring to sources of knowledge about sugar</p> <p>Confusion, misconceptions</p>	<p>Knowledge sources</p> <p>Dietary cacophony</p> <p>Scientific terms</p>
<p>France</p> <p><i>Juice is a huge source of sugar, without fibers ... Even natural juices and sugar-free are not recommended and can lead to caries ... Nothing is better than real fruit!</i></p> <p><i>Sugar from candy or juice has the same impact on our body.</i></p> <p><i>[Post] Smoothies? Consume with moderation and especially never between meals! The British Dental Association warns against smoothies, which are very concentrated in sugar and stick to the teeth, causing caries. In Great Britain, 25% of young children consume it. And you, do you give it to your child?</i></p> <p><i>By giving your kids a glass of juice or a smoothie rather than a soft drink, you usually think you're doing the right thing. False!</i></p> <p><i>Smoothie is not a drink that replaces water at the table !!!! THIS IS A DESSERT WITH MIXED FRUIT !!!!!!!</i></p> <p><i>Great, that's good to know, now I'm just going to eat chocolate...</i></p> <p><i>I prefer that he [son] drinks a fruit juice with water from time to time, rather than give him a coke filled with shit! Everyone can make their own choices, in my opinion.</i></p>	<p>Concern, uncertainty and frustration about healthiness of fruit juices and smoothies</p>	<p>Fruit juices and smoothies</p> <p>Dietary cacophony</p>

<p><i>A homemade smoothie for lunch or snack is not bad! Sugar from fruit is better than sugar in cake, that is not at all the same!</i></p> <p><i>Without added sugar, I don't see what the problem is [with smoothies]!!!</i></p> <p><i>I think they should talk about the smoothies found in the store, which does contain lots of sugars! not the ones we make ourselves, with only fruit and ice cubes</i></p> <p><i>When you read the ingredients of a container of juice and the only ingredient there is the fruit ... Yes there is sugar, that is to be expected, fruits are sweet!!! It is not free sugar, it is natural sugar, the same sugar that you would consume if you would eat the so-called fruit!!</i></p> <p>[answer to the above comment] <i>Yes but it's sugar without fiber, you can have 2-3 oranges in only 1 cup of juice, nobody would eat 3 oranges in one go because it would be full of fibers.</i></p>		
<p>France</p> <p><i>What about my pediatrician who told me to add sugar to my daughter's yogurt; she is 18 months old, because she is not gaining enough weight...(knowing that she eats more than the recommendations for her age and she is never sick) it annoys me.</i></p> <p><i>In my case, the doctor gave the green light for the sweetened yogurts knowing that this kind of baby yogurts is even sweeter than the other ones. He said that I could also take an unsweetened yogurt or cottage cheese and add a teaspoon of jam, for example.</i></p> <p><i>It is better to give already sweetened yogurts because we add too much sugar to plain yogurts (my pediatrician told me)</i></p>	<p>Pediatrician recommendation to child's unsatisfactory weight gain</p> <p>Annoyance towards health expert's recommendations</p>	<p>Knowledge sources</p> <p>Distrust on health experts</p>
<p>France</p> <p>[Talking about a TV show which discussed sugar in highly processed foods]</p> <p><i>That gentleman's remark [in the TV show's audience] made me laugh out loud "All this sugar is added to products with the government's permission?". Yes, yes my good sir, it's called the food industry lobby!!!</i></p> <p><i>Yes, children eat too much sugar. The sugar added in food products is purely marketing strategy, and it is not good for your health [...]. It's so harmful to your health!</i></p> <p><i>And yes, you understood well, sugar is addictive, our babies are the future consumers!!! Business is business!</i></p> <p><i>Yeeees, all they are saying [on the TV show] is true, without mentioning the waste produced by these shitty products found everywhere in nature.</i></p> <p><i>There is sugar everywhere, it's insane!! 😞</i></p> <p><i>They only sell us shit!</i></p>	<p>Marketing responsibility for children's overconsumption of sugar</p> <p>Marketers accused of lobbying and anti-ethical strategic methods to poison and addict children</p> <p>Consumers as victims to be protected by law and restrictions targeting the food industry</p>	<p>Highly processed foods</p> <p>Anger towards food manufacturers</p> <p>Marketing responsibility</p> <p>Lobbying and anti-ethical practices</p>

<p><i>They [the food industry] use our taxes... this is what we end up paying for, to be poisoned.</i></p> <p><i>Today we are surrounded by a sea of attractive products that are not so natural, without great nutritional value and toxic for the human body. We are not designed to eat food made by people in laboratories</i></p> <p><i>Instead of defending them [food industry], we should stop authorizing "crap" in children's food ...</i></p> <p><i>We should stop accusing parents! Accuse the government instead [for high sugar consumption]</i></p> <p><i>Well, when they [the food industry] stop adding sugar everywhere, the children will consume less sugar. It's simple.</i></p> <p><i>[in response to the comment above] I agree completely. If the food manufacturers reduce the sugar in their products, we would be much better off. Because unfortunately not all parents have time to cook everything from scratch (soup, jam, yogurt, baby foods, etc.)</i></p> <p><i>[in reaction to this comment: It's also up to parents not to buy super-sugary products ...]</i></p> <p><i>It is easier said than done. Our children are all attracted to these products and also, due to our lack of time and convenience of those products, we unfortunately consume them. Do not tell me that you have never bought or never consumed these products because I would not believe you.</i></p>	<p>Food industry as a dangerous force</p>	
<p>France</p> <p><i>It's also up to parents not to buy super-sugary products ...</i></p> <p><i>The primary responsibility lies with parents! In no case are we obliged to buy packets of cakes and ready-to-eat meals filled with sugar! Habits are difficult to change but it is definitely possible.</i></p> <p><i>No, but parents can read packaging, can't they?? No petition necessary for this.</i></p> <p><i>Just read the list of ingredients on the packaging before buying anything. It avoids unpleasant surprises.</i></p> <p><i>At home I give them a small piece [of candy] once a day, so no problem. I believe that we should do our job as parents and not give them [the children] too much</i></p> <p><i>Nobody needs to ingest aspartame, sulphites, monosodium glutamate, artificial sweeteners, sodium nitrate or benzoate ... We have to read [food labels], evaluate and choose. In short, it is necessary to be "responsible". It's not as if we did not know the facts, we are all aware now. Now we have to act consistently with what we know.</i></p> <p><i>WHAT??? Are these drinks too sweet ??? ☺☺ Seriously, just don't buy them, that's all !!! There is water and pure juices... no need for a petition to ban the stuff, just not buy it !!</i></p>	<p>Defending a proactive posture of personal and parental responsibility as food providers</p> <p>Consumers depicted as accountable and capable of avoiding unhealthy choices by checking food labels</p> <p>Prohibition of sugary foods from the market as "insane" and "non-sense"</p> <p>Liberation of highly processed foods as incompatible with responsible parental guidance</p>	<p>Parental responsibility</p> <p>Responsible parenting and health</p> <p>Food labels</p> <p>Consumer autonomy</p> <p>Judgmental moral tone</p>

<p><i>Simply by trying to change habits we already show our children a good example. We can rethink our lifestyle to try to improve it. We are responsible for what we consume. The marketing is not what drives our actions. It's a great experience [sugar free period]!</i></p> <p><i>I don't believe it!!! If it's too sweet, just don't give it to your little ones, that's all !!!</i></p> <p><i>Seriously, a petition to ban candy? Ha-ha, parents are responsible for feeding their children. Stop the madness</i></p>		
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>What the fuck. The institutions get so hysterical and boring at that point. We have started our own private institutions and there we do not have a sugar policy, but in return, we work with what is called common sense. We encourage parents to choose something other than a big cake full of cream.</i></p> <p><i>I HATE dietary policy.</i></p> <p><i>There is zero sugar policy in the municipality, but I do not think they should decide what our children get, which is my responsibility as a parent.</i></p> <p><i>Great for us non-fanatical parents ... [...] Frankly, I think it's up to each parent to tell themselves if they think their child shouldn't have what is on the table.</i></p> <p><i>We know it. Sugar in such large quantities is not good for some bodies. But it's SO hard to talk about because it interferes with our personal freedom of action.</i></p> <p><i>It is no secret that I think that all children have the right to get exactly as much sugar as their parents decide.</i></p> <p><i>I think it has gone too far – this sugar hysteria! It's too much!</i></p> <p><i>My God, poor children ... no one has died yet from koldskål [a traditional Danish dessert]. It was kind of a buffet table where you could choose what you wanted, so I don't see the problem at all: – / all the sugar-scared zombies could just eat a lettuce leaf, no sorry ... but I get so angry when someone wants decide what others can have.</i></p> <p><i>The shit sugar policy [at schools]. What do they care what OUR children eat.</i></p>	<p>Criticism towards schools' food policies</p> <p>Defending personal and parental responsibility</p> <p>Zero-sugar approach as hysterical and non-sense</p> <p>Defending personal freedom for food choices</p>	<p>"No-sugar" policy</p> <p>Parental autonomy</p> <p>Parental responsibility</p> <p>Personal freedom</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>Both of my kids have attended / attend 100 percent sugar-free institutions (and no, by the way, we don't live sugar-free at home), and that has NEVER been a problem.</i></p> <p><i>I have loved my children's institutions and respected them for maintaining their policies ...</i></p> <p><i>Well, I'm not fanatical, but actually thought that all institutions should have a sugar policy</i></p>	<p>In favor of schools' non-sugar policies</p>	<p>Schools responsibility</p>

France	Codes	Themes/sub-themes
<p><i>By teaching good eating habits, I think we are giving the best legacy ever !!</i></p> <p><i>and I do believe we are giving him the best legacy ever !!</i></p> <p>[in response to a TV show discussing the sugar content of processed foods] <i>To avoid to avoid to avoid as much as possible!!!! Help!!!!</i></p> <p><i>I never buy popcorn and all that junk that has been sitting on the shelves for ages by the time we eat. He [son] will not eat it until he turns 38!</i></p> <p><i>I also try to limit [sugar] as much as possible for my children. I myself am a sugar addict, and that is not a manner of speech! I am in permanent withdrawal, I relapse constantly, it is very hard.</i></p> <p><i>Our children are completely addicted it is absolutely necessary to re-educate ourselves: the human body is not adapted to consume this much sugar! Until recently it was a rare thing in our diets ... we have to remember that!</i></p> <p><i>Same here, zero candy, only water or pomegranate juice / fresh orange juice, cookies and cakes low in sugar, mashed fruit instead of jam, dark chocolate instead of milk chocolate. Our 3-year old son loves it and he is not missing out on anything because his palate has been educated, it has not been swamped with sugar ...</i></p>	<p>Restriction justified on the grounds of harmful health effects of sugar (addiction, obesity), and the importance of influencing children's palate and promoting health</p>	<p>Behavioral strategy: restriction</p> <p>Health effect: addiction, decreased palatability</p> <p>Alarming tone</p> <p>Core value (health)</p>
<p>Denmark</p>		
<p><i>I struggle with sugar addiction myself and I get so happy when I'm at meetings where there are delicious healthy alternatives and a good atmosphere around the healthy stuff. And I am 45 years old and need help ;-). So, hell, give those kids a good diet / healthy start.</i></p> <p><i>Yes I belong to the scared sugar ones, mostly because I myself have the worst habits that I wish I had never started, because they are tough habits to break.</i></p> <p>[...] <i>the earlier children are exposed to sugar, the more sugar they will eat as adults [...]</i> And there I think you have to look out for your child's health, also in adulthood.</p> <p><i>And we know that 70% of those who are obese as children take their excess weight into adulthood. So there is really good reason to take a preventive approach here!</i></p>		
<p>France</p>	<p>Codes</p>	<p>Themes/sub-themes</p>
<p><i>why restrict ??? just eat in moderation and occasionally</i></p> <p><i>I think that the main thing is to eat a balanced diet and I think that also includes junk. The main thing is not to overdo it. My children are forbidden nothing but nothing is consumed in excess, and they practice physical exercise.</i></p>	<p>"Everything in moderation" aphorism</p>	<p>Behavioral strategy: moderation</p>

<p><i>Banning certain foods completely can lead to an unhealthy relation with food. Eating a little bit of junk occasionally is not bad.</i></p>		
<p>Denmark</p>		
<p><i>But he can also get sweets on other days apart from Friday. Everything in moderation.</i></p> <p><i>As I said EVERYTHING IN MODERATION – sugars as well as milk, artificial colorings, wheat, etc. ...</i></p>		
<p>France</p>	<p>Liberation on the grounds of the importance given to hedonic, symbolic aspects of sugar</p>	<p>Symbolic, hedonic aspects</p>
<p><i>We just have a little dessert for dinner! You have to enjoy food pleasure too !!!</i></p> <p><i>No prohibition, it creates temptations. We eat very well, we allow ourselves gastronomic pleasures</i></p>		<p>Pursuit of enjoyment</p>
<p>Denmark</p>		<p>Gastronomic pleasures</p>
<p><i>NO RULES IN SUMMER – IF IT TASTES GOOD</i></p> <p><i>No rules in the summer as to ice cream – this rule we also live by 😊😊 Try vanilla ice with popcorn in it... It is MEGA delicious 😊 How lovely, happy, and safe the kids were<3</i></p> <p><i>I take that view on board – of course, people can be as fanatical as they want, but in my opinion, the idea of not enjoying yourself is simply too much.</i></p> <p><i>I LOVE being with my kids around the table in the afternoon for a "forbidden" pancake and a chat about life.</i></p>		
<p>Denmark</p>	<p>Liberation to ensure a sensible, healthy relation with sugar</p>	<p>Sensible relation with sugar</p>
<p><i>We believe that everyone gets the most sensible relationship with food by forbidding nothing</i></p> <p><i>Here, a healthy relationship with all kinds of food is the most important thing.</i></p> <p><i>I think that sounds totally crazy [zero sugar policy at schools]. As a child of a family with a "zero sugar" policy, I would like to add that throughout my adult life I have struggled to find a sensible balance in my relationship with food. A balance I still haven't found. It is so deeply rooted in me that sugar is forbidden that I end up eating it all the time rather than enjoying it a little – I simply never learned that. It is either "nothing" or "everything".</i></p> <p><i>Giving him [son] a sensible relationship with sweet things is just as important to us as giving him a sensible relationship with alcohol when he hits his teens.</i></p>	<p>Opposing deprivation and extreme strategies</p>	
<p>France</p>	<p>Opposing a paranoid, fanatical, hysterical attitude</p>	<p>Societal judgment</p>
<p><i>There is sugar / salt / fat in everything so we have to stop being paranoid . We can never completely make the sugar disappear from our diet</i></p> <p><i>I also don't want to make him [son] an alien who is not allowed any candies!</i></p>	<p>Opposing deprivation and extreme strategies</p>	<p>Judgmental moral tone</p> <p>Social aspects</p>

Denmark		
<p><i>I make sure my son tastes all food groups in a day, but no sugar hysteria here.</i></p> <p><i>Prohibition and hysteria create little sugar-hungry monsters who cannot control themselves.</i></p> <p><i>I am an educator and totally agree that it is hysteria that does not benefit.</i></p> <p><i>I don't even have children yet and I'm also very annoyed with all that hysteria.</i></p> <p><i>My youngest of 2 years doesn't get sugar yet – and he doesn't really care, either. So maybe I go in the "sugar hysterical" category.</i></p>	Zero-sugar approach as hysterical and non-sense	Rejection/Acceptance of a healthy-focused identity
France	Other values more important than healthy eating, including freedom and autonomy	Sensible relation with sugar
<p><i>By restricting everything too much, we end up in anxiety-provoking and toxic relationships with food, much more toxic than sugar. Long live chocolate, long live freedom to feast, children and adults!</i></p>		
Denmark	Importance given to hedonic, symbolic aspects of sugar	Social and hedonic aspects
<p><i>Well, in fact – there are actually more dangerous things in the world than sugar, and maybe we should soon abandon the morality towards our children, and not force them to live the life [without sugar] that we ourselves have no guts to accomplish</i></p> <p><i>I love sweets, my kids love sweets and we love to eat sweets together 😊😊</i></p>	Sweets as important for parent-child bonding	Symbolic value of sugar
Extract	Codes	Themes/sub-themes
MAJOR THEME 1) Sugar-related concerns, beliefs and practices		
1.2 Child-focused content		
Social aspects		
France	Judgment by a stranger at the supermarket for denying to buy chocolate for her child	Parental judgment
<p>[Post]</p> <p><i>This morning I was shopping with my kid. Of course, he tried to fill our cart with candies, cookies and other "super-balanced" foods.</i></p> <p><i>I said to him: "Darling, no candy, it is not good for your health, it is full of sugar, and besides, you have it at home.</i></p> <p><i>He took out the cookies [...]. Suddenly a lady behind me gets interrupts our talk and tells me: "you know, it's not a few candies that will kill him, it's not that bad"</i></p> <p><i>oO</i></p> <p><i>ugggh, excuse me madam, it does not occur to you that I am trying to teach my son to have a minimally balanced diet? No, because hey, it's ok to say yes to everything and let them stuff themselves with candy, cookies [...]</i></p> <p><i>In short, there is always someone to tell you how to raise your kids. (yes I know I am a grumpy : p)</i></p>		Judgmental moral tone
France	Parents criticized for being	Societal Judgment

<p>[Comments on the above post] <i>And then if you had taken the candies and cakes your son asked for, you would have been told "you allow your child everything, it's shameful" !!!!!</i></p> <p><i>If you had bought candy, the woman would have told you that it is not good for his health</i></p> <p><i>Hey but you know what, I was criticized because my daughter was eating cherry tomatoes at [a certain supermarket chain]</i> <i>When we don't behave like the majority, we are criticized. [...] Our 3-year-old son adores healthy foods, and it is not a torture because his palate has been educated not to be submerged in sugar ... Nevertheless, he participates in birthdays and eats sweets occasionally.</i></p> <p><i>Good luck to the alien parents who try not to force-feed their children with sugars and Mc Donald's ☺ good luck</i></p> <p><i>Yes! I am classified as a super strict mother who prevents her son from drinking something other than soft drinks but he doesn't like it</i></p> <p><i>It's easy to give kids sugar in abundance, maybe thinking it's a way to make them happy ... and when you don't want to give them sugar at all (lollipops, fizzy drinks ...) other people tell you that you are not nice, they look at you as if you come from outer space ...</i></p>	<p>too strict or too permissive</p> <p>Unescapable societal judgment on parental role and practices</p> <p>Opposite views: restriction versus liberation</p> <p>Opposing deprivation and extreme strategies</p>	<p>Concept of self and values</p> <p>Acceptance/Rejection of a health-focused identity</p> <p>Core values</p> <p>Judgmental moral tone</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>My God, poor children [referring to zero-sugar policy at schools]... no one has died yet of koldskål [Danish traditional dessert] with sweet rusks. It was kind of a buffet table where people could choose what they wanted, so I don't see the problem at all: –/ all the sugar-scared zombies could just eat a lettuce leaf, no sorry ...</i></p> <p><i>Because in these finger-pointing and sugar-phobic times we live in, there are almost similarities between sugar and cocaine. "The White Devil". "Sugar-Satan".</i></p> <p><i>I'm just so tired of sugar-scared parents.</i></p> <p><i>I do not agree. And I think that discourse is going too far "see how much sugar we give our children, see how rebellious we are!". And I can't understand that you have to be labelled as a freaky-mother because you want your kids to eat healthy</i></p> <p><i>THANK YOU [the author of a posts discouraging sugar consumption] for fucking sake. Because you are labelled, a hysterical mother who only wants to hurt her children if you restrict sugar.</i></p> <p><i>Sometimes it feels more provocative to say that you do not give your children Friday sweets than to say that you serve them Matadormix [kind of candy] for breakfast.</i></p>		

<p><i>Sugar has become an everyday thing. And if you say no, you are strange, or just rude.</i></p> <p><i>My youngest of 2 years doesn't get sugar yet – and he doesn't really care, either. So maybe I go in the "sugar hysterical" category.</i></p> <p><i>Am sure the curling parents choked on their organic sugar-free lactose-free café latte this morning, which is great!</i></p> <p><i>Hysteria of the worst kind – my big daughter went to a similar institution [with zero sugar policy] but my 3-year-old goes to a really nice institution.</i> <i>I think it's very weird to be so hysterical about food.</i></p> <p><i>Totally agree! This extreme attitude is simply too much.</i></p> <p><i>So I totally agree that there is always a mommy mafia out there, ready to point their fingers, in the true mafia style. Only because you use a non-organic diaper brand</i></p> <p><i>I am often accused of being scared of sugar, and that's okay, because I am.</i></p> <p><i>I am so lucky that my children do not like soft drinks, but I often find that when we attend social events (also in the family) there is only fizzy drinks. So when I ask for water, the host either thinks “those poor kids” or that I'm 'evil' because they don't get soft drinks.</i></p> <p><i>Children and sugar – a minefield, I know. But I really think we need to be able to talk about it. So we are off course here.</i></p>		
<p>France</p> <p><i>When Mister Daddy goes shopping and brings Mr. Frozen desserts saying that it is just a joke ... Yeah yeah yeah 😊</i></p>	<p>Father's role as permissive about sweet consumption</p>	<p>Gendered practice</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>If he wants candies, he asks his dad</i></p>		
<p>Extract</p>	<p>Codes</p>	<p>Themes/sub-themes</p>
<p>MAJOR THEME 2) Attitudes to anti-sugar messages</p>		
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>In fact, I once heard a diet / exercise guru of some kind say that she herself always adds sugar to her oatmeal. If that's what it took for the kids to get some healthy, nutritious food to start the day, then it would be SO much better than not adding sugar.</i></p> <p><i>Sugar is energy</i></p> <p><i>But before sugar is proclaimed as evil itself, it's important to note that sugar is a fuel source like anything else your child eats..</i></p>	<p>Nutrition messages with a less negative approach to sugar in Denmark</p>	<p>Sugar-related messages in Denmark</p> <p>Knowledge sources</p> <p>Positive meanings attributed to sugar</p>

<p><i>I am happy with the article because it not only emphasizes the white sugar, which is unhealthy, but also that there are many different kinds of sugar and that sugar is something the body needs to function.</i></p>		
<p>Denmark <i>My son is 18 months old and loves sweet things, just like his mother! Many people may think that he gets too much, but every meal of the day we eat healthy and organic.</i></p> <p><i>The most important thing for me is no longer how little or how much sugar my children get, but more that there should always be room for proper food too.</i></p>	<p>Sugar consumption liberated as soon as healthy foods are also eaten</p>	<p>Healthy foods to compensate sugar intake</p>
<p>Denmark <i>In fact, children are born with a sweet tooth, it's because they live on breastmilk which is very sweet. Who knows... maybe that's why they keep being so cute ;-)</i></p> <p><i>We are born liking sweet tastes or at least learn it pretty early.</i></p>	<p>Inner fondness of sugar by babies as an indication of its legitimacy</p>	<p>Sugar as legitimate</p> <p>Positive meanings attributed to sugar</p>
<p>France <i>Everything, even water is said to be unhealthy! Eating is stressful, we feel guilty and we are afraid of everything we swallow ... there are so many restrictions and recommendations that I don't want to eat at all anymore.</i></p> <p><i>But is there still something we can eat??</i></p> <p><i>Ughh, seriously, hold your horses, if we listen to it all, we won't eat anything!</i></p> <p><i>So what do I give him [son]? Coffee? Tea? Whiskey?</i></p> <p><i>If we listen to all this, we won't eat anything anymore!!!</i></p> <p><i>Also, I find it quite difficult to make sense of all that I hear about food today, which almost requires us to stop breathing, to stop consuming everything, air included, because it's dangerous...</i></p> <p><i>great we no longer know what to feed our children</i></p>	<p>Expressing distress, anxiety and feelings of impotence towards dietary discourses</p> <p>Feelings of helplessness</p> <p>Conflict between sugar and fat debate</p>	<p>Dietary cacophony</p> <p>Frustration towards dietary discourses</p> <p>Fear of fat</p> <p>Fear of food</p> <p>Negative emotions</p>
<p>Denmark <i>It's always good to have the sugar debate in mind, but it shouldn't be the only thing. Fiber and fat are also part of it. There is less fat in a chocolate sandwich than a salami sausage sandwich. What are you giving your child?</i></p> <p><i>When I was a kid, fat was the root of all evil and some families completely dropped fats in their children's food.</i></p> <p><i>I totally agree with you. And especially when some parents start claiming that fruit is also unhealthy due to fruit sugar. It's so nice to see that you are not sugar scared and your kids are allowed to have some candy 😊</i></p>		
<p>Extract</p>	<p>Codes</p>	<p>Themes/sub-themes</p>

MAJOR THEME 2) Attitudes to anti-sugar messages		
Acceptance		
<p>France</p> <p>[in response to a TV show discussing the sugar content of processed foods] <i>We will quit the Nesquick</i></p> <p><i>Yeah that's for sure, me too. We have already reduced the high-sugary cereals in the morning by replacing them with jam sandwiches but I'm going to purge all that out from my cupboards!</i></p> <p><i>The truth about food products ... That it is always good to keep in mind ...</i></p> <p><i>In our house, we banned all these foods a long time ago less sugar = better health !!! Thank you for sharing</i> 👉👎👈</p> <p><i>I'm going to buy this book, so we can have a good selection of products in our cupboards!</i></p> <p>[in response to a TV show discussing the sugar content of processed foods] <i>The food that is valued in our society is unhealthy and we have to learn to choose well. I don't think it's [highly processed food] the kind of thing that will kill you instantly, but the kind of thing that over the years accumulates in your body and ends up causing all kinds of health problems. Today we are surrounded by a sea of attractive products that are not so natural, without great nutritional value and toxic for the human body. We are not designed to eat food made by people in laboratories</i></p> <p><i>We can't talk about these things in conferences because they are well funded by Nestle and company 😊 I study sugar in my laboratory and it blows my mind every day to be aware of such a crisis: we bathe in sugar, it's a crime (look at school canteens 😞) our children are completely addicted..... it is absolutely necessary to re-educate ourselves: the human body is not designed to consume this much sugar! Until recently it was a rare commodity in our diets ... this must be remembered!</i></p> <p><i>Thank you to the food industry for poisoning us and our children with excessive sugar and salt!</i></p> <p><i>They only sell us shit!</i></p> <p><i>Look [tagging someone with a male name]... we give trash to our son</i> <i>Ah yes, frankly it's a shame ... for me, who drinks it [Nesquick®] every morning ...</i></p> <p><i>Outrageous!!!!</i></p>	<p>Assimilation and acceptance of the anti-sugar message</p> <p>Demonstrating intention to change behavior</p> <p>Indignation against the food industry</p> <p>Food industry as a dangerous force</p> <p>Demonstration of health as a core value and ego-involvement with anti-sugar messages</p>	<p>Acceptance</p> <p>Intention to change behavior</p> <p>Anger towards food manufacturers</p> <p>Highly processed foods</p> <p>Ego-involvement</p> <p>Core values</p>

<p><i>I'm shocked! Not kidding...</i></p> <p><i>Let's reduce the sugar and the junk!</i></p> <p><i>This is disgusting! we exchanged our usual chocolate powder for ... but in fact, the new one is no better!</i></p>		
<p>France</p>	<p>Valuing responsible parenting practices and health by advocating sugar restriction</p>	<p>Health as a core value and concept of self</p>
<p><i>We must protect our children</i></p> <p><i>Avoid all forms of sugars for your children as much as possible, and find out about the harmful effects of sugar on our bodies.</i></p> <p><i>NOOO !! nowadays people give their children no matter what!!</i></p> <p><i>Yes again about sugar, and yes we demonize sugar. Because let's be honest, sugar does nothing good! Millions of adults (including me) suffer from sugar addiction because of a childhood with too much sugar</i></p>	<p>Demonstration of health as a core value and ego-involvement with anti-sugar messages</p>	<p>Ego-involvement</p> <p>Responsible parenting and health</p> <p>Judgmental moral tone</p>
<p>Denmark</p>		<p>Acceptance of a health-focused identity</p>
<p><i>Yes I belong to the scared sugar ones, mostly because I myself have the worst habits that I wish I had never started</i></p> <p><i>No, children under 3 should NOT have sugar. That's what research says – children under the age of 3 simply don't need sugar!</i></p> <p><i>Our children will know that we had enough knowledge to act on. My mother may say “we didn't know it [effects of sugar on health] then”, but now we know better. I am not saying that there should be a prohibition, but we have to take responsibility.</i></p> <p><i>Yes – I'm a little bit fanatic, anyone would think. But I think it sounds really nice that a child of 2 or 3 years has not tasted either gummy bears or an ice cream waffle.</i></p> <p><i>I have no idea what to think about it. On the one hand, I am a low carb mom – who thinks this is no go and that sugary things should be kept to a minimum.</i></p>		
<p>Extract</p>	<p>Codes</p>	<p>Themes/sub-themes</p>
<p>MAJOR THEME 2) Attitudes to anti-sugar messages</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Non-commitment</p>		
<p>France</p>		
<p><i>Parents who want to give their children sugar, great! Those who don't, great too ”!</i></p>		

<p><i>It is useless to feel guilty, if other moms do more than we do, good for them, each of us has our own character, needs and availability</i></p>	<p>Indifference and neutrality towards anti-sugar messages</p>	<p>Indifference</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>People can give their children whatever they want. Don't be fooled by other people's choices or upbringing. I just get pretty annoyed by this recurring sugar debate 😊</i></p> <p><i>People can do what they want and fill their children with exactly what they want. These aren't my kids, so I don't care much.</i></p> <p><i>Soooo... now comes a slightly delicate topic (for anyone!). Fortunately, I don't care.</i></p> <p><i>Sugar / non-sugar: I don't care what others do. Whether they are sugar scared or not.</i></p>	<p>Weak ego-involvement with anti-sugar messages</p>	<p>Weak ego-involvement</p>
<p>France</p> <p><i>Frankly, I find a solution "in-between" very satisfactory because I can still enjoy sweets (less often, certainly), the craving and the taste buds are satisfied. This allows a not so brutal weaning. And this is a solution that I see myself applying over a very long time since it brings no frustration ...</i></p> <p><i>Balance is key</i></p>	<p>Adopting a position "in the middle", balance as a core value</p> <p>"Everything in moderation" aphorism</p>	<p>Concept of self: balanced, parsimonious</p> <p>Behavioral strategy: moderation</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>My girl is allowed some on and off. Would like to give her a normal, healthy and balanced relationship with food.</i></p> <p><i>Everything in moderation. As long as the relationship between healthy food and unhealthy food makes sense.</i></p> <p><i>Here there is nothing our children are not allowed to do, but we say "everything in moderation".</i></p> <p><i>We also have no rules regarding candy in everyday life, all with in moderation</i></p> <p><i>We probably run a Yin-Yang principle where there has to be a balance.</i></p> <p><i>We are all different, parents, employees and children, so of course there is no "right way" :-)</i></p> <p><i>We have a relaxed relationship with sugar. We live by "everything in moderation principle".</i></p>		
<p>Extract</p>	<p>Codes</p>	<p>Themes/sub-themes</p>
<p>MAJOR THEME 2) Attitudes to anti-sugar messages</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Rejection</p>		
<p>France</p> <p><i>Even water is sometimes harmful; certain brands are even very harmful. So stop, leave us alone because we are already stressed!!</i></p>		<p>Dietary cacophony</p>

<p><i>But is there still something we can eat?? Ughh, seriously, you have to hold your horses, if we listen to it all we eat nothing!</i></p> <p><i>Also, I find it quite difficult to make sense of all that I hear about food today, which almost requires us to stop breathing, to stop consuming everything, air included, because it's dangerous ...</i></p> <p><i>No fruit juice, no cookies, no chocolate, no cereals ... wow, I imagine my children's reaction if I only give them nuts and water ...</i></p> <p><i>Everything, even water is said to be unhealthy! Eating is stressful, we feel guilty and we are afraid of everything we swallow ... there are so many restrictions and recommendations that I don't want to eat anymore.</i></p> <p><i>Leave us parents alone, bloody hell.</i></p>	<p>Expressing distress, anxiety and feelings of impotence towards dietary discourses</p> <p>Feelings of helplessness</p> <p>Anxiety, distress, impotence, discouragement</p> <p>Public recommendations of sugar as extreme and impossible to follow</p>	<p>Fear of food</p> <p>Frustration towards dietary discourses</p> <p>Negative emotions</p>
<p>Denmark</p>		
<p><i>God damn! I don't even have children yet and I also get very annoyed by all that hysteria.</i></p> <p><i>I don't mean that schools should serve sugar on an everyday basis, but stop the damn hysteria! Well, if there is a party, let there be a party! I just get so annoyed with all this sanctimoniousness.</i></p> <p><i>Young people are brainwashed into believing that sugar is the downfall of the earth</i></p> <p><i>My kids love candy ... and they get it Let's hope they survive as everyone else has done so far; -) ... Jesus Christ ...</i></p>		
<p>France</p>		
<p><i>Completely agree with you, everything is a pretext to make the parents feel guilty [...]</i></p> <p><i>Come on, we must stop this ... It is tiring with all these moral-lesson givers as if people were idiots.</i></p> <p>[mentioning another member of the group] <i>ah thank yooooou I felt very alone with the moralizing attacks of some 😊</i></p>	<p>Public discourses on sugar considered moralistic, authoritarian, judgmental</p> <p>Parents criticized for being too strict or too permissive</p>	<p>Judgmental moral tone</p> <p>Parental judgment</p> <p>Frustration towards dietary discourses</p>
<p>Denmark</p>		
<p><i>This fight against sugar, overweight in which sugar determines whether we are good or bad parents. The parents who are capable of being strict towards their children and who are able to offer the children good, healthy and natural alternatives to white sugar are the good parents. They are labelled the ones who take care of the child for its future, body and mind. All of us, who are in between [...] we are inferior parents.</i></p> <p><i>I'm tired of hearing what "experts" have to say</i></p> <p><i>I think the focus of these articles [on detrimental effects of sugar] is absolutely crazy 😡</i></p>	<p>Opposing deprivation and extreme strategies</p>	<p>Negative emotions</p> <p>Rejection of a health-focused identity</p>

<p><i>Oh, for crying out loud. It is this kind of article that creates strict mothers, with their perfect glycemic indexes, and not least the bad conscience of parents. My child gets too much sugar and white bread, I admit it</i></p>		
<p>France</p> <p><i>By restricting everything, we end up in anxiety-provoking and toxic mindsets, much more toxic than sugar, long live the freedom to feast and enjoy, children and adults!</i></p> <p><i>I guess people posting comments here have never eaten at Mc Donald's 😊😊😊. Oh yes, eat only fruit and vegetables from their garden, don't smoke, don't drink, eat green, that's real life 😊😊😊damm</i></p> <p><i>My children drink it [Nesquick®] and will continue to do so. I also eat unhealthy, I am overweight, and between you and me and the bedpost, we don't care what other people think. If my children want those foods, I will not prohibit it, and if they do not like vegetables, I will not force them either. It's time to leave the parents alone, bloody hell.</i></p>	<p>Codes</p> <p>Defending personal freedom for food choices</p> <p>Other values more important than healthy eating, including freedom and autonomy</p> <p>Sweets as important for parent-child bonding</p>	<p>Themes/sub-themes</p> <p>Rejection of a healthy-focused identity</p> <p>Transgressive identity</p> <p>Concept of self</p> <p>Personal freedom</p> <p>Social and hedonic aspects</p> <p>Symbolic value of sugar</p>
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>I'm a sugar junkie too – and proud of it!</i></p> <p><i>I was absolutely delighted when an educator told me [...] that my boy had eaten about three times as much [chocolate balls] as the others. That's nice. Both he and I have a serious sweet tooth”</i></p> <p><i>I love sweets, my kids love sweets and we love to eat sweets together 😊😊</i></p>		
<p>Denmark</p> <p><i>I think I have actually changed during motherhood; that I have become significantly more relaxed over the years.</i></p> <p><i>With my oldest child, I was quite hysterical about sugar, whereas with little brother I am more loose. And what a relief to myself!</i></p>		<p>Less concerns after the 2nd child</p>